

ADSORPTION OF IONS BY HYDRATED MANGANESE DIOXIDE IN
RELATION TO ITS ELECTRICAL CHARGE AND THE CON-
CENTRATION OF THE HYDROGEN IONS LIBERATED

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The adsorption of ions from solutions of chlorides of some alkali and alkaline earth metals by hydrated manganese dioxide has been investigated. It has been shown that the cations are adsorbed in appreciable quantities and that the adsorption of the chloride ions although negligible from a solution of KCl, is quite marked from the solutions of BaCl₂, CaCl₂ and MgCl₂. The adsorption of cations are accompanied by the liberation of H⁺ ions and in the case of the divalent cations this has been attributed to their adsorption both (1) in the electrically adsorbed and (2) in the mobile parts of the electrical double layer at the solid/liquid interface.

The adsorption of cations from solutions of electrolytes by hydrated manganese dioxide has been investigated by Van Bemmelen (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1881, 23, 324, 327), Mehrotra and Sen (*this Journal*, 1926, 3, 297), Ghosh (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2605), Chakravarty and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 21, 997) and Levy (*Ann. chim.*, 1931, vii, 13, 85). It has been observed that in such adsorption, H⁺ ions are liberated in appreciable quantities. The liberation of H⁺ ions has been attributed by Ghosh (*loc. cit.*) and by Mukherjee (*this Journal*, 1925, 2, 191; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3023) to the displacement of the H⁺ ions from the electrical double layer by cations entering into this layer from the solution. Chlopin and Balandin (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1925, 149, 157) have also investigated the interaction of manganese dioxide with electrolytes like BaCl₂, and have concluded that the liberation of acid can be represented by the following chemical equation

If this view be correct, it would mean that each Ba⁺⁺ ion which reacts with manganese dioxide should liberate two H⁺ ions and no Cl⁻ ions should be adsorbed. From a consideration of the reversal of electrical charge of hydrated manganese dioxide in the presence of chlorides of divalent cations like Ba⁺⁺, Ghosh (*loc. cit.*) has predicted that the adsorption of each Ba⁺⁺ ion should be accompanied by liberation of one H⁺ ion and adsorption of one Cl⁻ ion. The observation of Chakravarty and Dhar (*loc. cit.*) that the number of gram equivalents of HCl liberated is less than the number of gram equivalents of Ba⁺⁺ adsorbed seems to support the view expressed by Ghosh (*loc. cit.*). To test the different view points recorded above, it is necessary that a systematic determination of the cations adsorbed and the H⁺ ions liberated should be made. The results of such measurements along with that of the electrical charge of hydrated manganese dioxide in the presence of different electrolytes are recorded in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

In the preparation of samples of manganese dioxide a 10% solution of manganous sulphate was mixed with a slight excess of a concentrated solution of potassium

permanganate in presence of sulphuric acid. The precipitate of manganese dioxide thus formed was washed repeatedly with hot distilled water, the washing being continued for over a period of eight days, when the p_H of the wash liquid rose to about 5.2, and it was free from SO_4^{2-} ion. It was then washed with conductivity water until the p_H rose to 5.6. The precipitate was then stored in a well-stoppered bottle. The percentage, of moisture and manganese dioxide were determined and the composition of the sample in stoichiometric formula was found to be $6.16 MnO_2, MnO, 43.15 H_2O$.

Effect of the Bivalent Cations on the Electrical Charge of Manganese Dioxide.—The effect of the bivalent cations on the electrical charge of manganese dioxide was measured by the electro-osmotic method. The arrangement used for the electro-osmotic experiments was similar to that used by Mukherjee and co-workers (*Nature*, 1922, 110, 732) and was described fully by Ghosh and Roy (this *Journal*, 1939, 16, 644).

It will be noticed from the data given in Table I that the capacity of the bivalent cations to diminish the negative charge is in one order : $Ba > Ca > Mg$.

TABLE I

Electro-osmotic experiments.

Potential difference between the terminals of the electrodes was 200 volts.

Movement of air bubbles in (mm./min.)				Movement of air bubbles (mm./min.)			
Conc.	BaCl ₂	CaCl ₂	MgCl ₂	Conc.	BaCl ₂	CaCl ₂	MgCl ₂
N/5	+22.0	+19.0	+17.2	N/50	+ 5.0	+ 4.2	+ 2.1
N/15	+16.0	+14.0	—	N/60	+ 3.0	+ 1.8	— 1.4
N/25	+11.2	—	—	N/80	— 2.5	— 3.2	— 4.1

* † Sign indicates that the MnO_2 has become positively charged and *vice versa*.

Determination of the H⁺ Ions liberated and of the Adsorption of the Cations and Anions.—The adsorption of the ions was determined by using 4 g. of manganese dioxide and 100 c.c. of the solution of the electrolyte in question, in different bottles. Each bottle was shaken in a mechanical shaker for 15 minutes. The contents of the bottle were then allowed to settle, as much of the clear supernatant solution as possible was withdrawn and analysed. The barium was precipitated as sulphate using pure dilute sulphuric acid. The calcium was estimated by precipitating it as calcium oxalate, washing, and then dissolving the precipitate in dilute sulphuric acid, boiling and titrating the oxalic acid liberated against standard permanganate solution. The magnesium was estimated by precipitating it as magnesium ammonium phosphate, and igniting the latter to pyrophosphate. The acid was estimated by titration with N/50 solution of baryta using phenolphthalein as an indicator and the chloride was estimated gravimetrically as AgCl. The results are recorded in Table II. In Table III are recorded some data on the adsorption of barium, calcium and potassium from solutions of their acetates and chlorides side by side for comparison. The potassium was estimated by evaporating a definite volume of the solution of its salts and then converting them into sulphate.

TABLE II

Conc.	No. of mg. ions of			2M-A.	Conc.	No. of mg. ions of			2M-A.
	metal adsorbed.	Cl adsorbed.	H liberated 'H'.			metal adsorbed.	Cl adsorbed.	H liberated 'H'.	
		BaCl ₂				CaCl ₂			
N/10	0.604	0.136	1.080	1.072	N/10	0.309	0.115	0.507	0.503
N/20	0.562	0.098	1.050	1.026	N/20	0.279	0.094	0.477	0.464
N/30	0.517	0.072	0.976	0.962	N/30	0.255	0.075	0.449	0.435
N/40	0.475	0.048	0.913	0.902	N/40	0.234	0.052	0.421	0.416
		MgCl ₂				MgCl ₂			
N/10	0.442	0.038	0.850	0.846	N/10	0.234	0.082	0.403	0.386
N/20	0.416	0.034	0.802	0.798	N/20	0.214	0.064	0.352	0.364
					N/30	0.195	0.045	0.334	0.345
					N/40	0.180	0.031	0.319	0.329

TABLE III

 BaCl₂ — Ba(Ac)₂*

Conc.	No. of mg. ions of Ba adsorbed from		No. of mg. mol. of acid liberated from		No. of mg. anions absorbed (calc. from eqn. 1)	
	BaCl ₂	Ba(Ac) ₂	BaCl ₂	Ba(Ac) ₂	Cl.	Ac.
N/10	0.604	1.263	1.080	2.402	0.128	0.124
N/20	0.562	1.085	1.050	2.084	0.074	0.084
N/30	0.517	0.987	0.976	1.885	0.058	0.089
N/40	0.475	—	0.913	—	0.037	—
N/50	0.442	0.813	0.850	1.562	0.034	0.064

* Ac stands for acetate ion.

Acids from chloride solutions means hydrochloric acid, and from acetates, means acetic acid.

TABLE IV

 CaCl₂—Ca(Ac)₂

KCl—KAc

Conc.	No. of mg. ions of Ca adsorbed from		No. of mg. mol. of acid liberated from		No. of mg. anions adsorbed (calc. from eqn. 1).		Conc.	No. of mg. ions of K adsorbed from		No. of mg. mol. of acid liberated from		No. of mg. anions adsorbed calc. from eqn. 1).	
	CaCl ₂	Ca(Ac) ₂	CaCl ₂	Ca(Ac) ₂	Cl.	Ac.		KCl.	KAc.	KCl.	KAc.	Cl.	Ac.*
N/10	0.309	1.045	0.507	2.001	0.111	0.089	N/10	0.547	1.856	0.524	1.841	0.023	0.015
N/20	0.279	0.935	0.477	1.799	0.081	0.071	N/20	0.501	1.700	0.485	1.684	0.016	0.016
N/30	0.255	0.859	0.449	1.663	0.061	0.055	N/30	0.450	1.480	0.435	1.466	0.015	0.014
N/40	0.234	0.784	0.421	1.543	0.047	0.025	N/40	0.440	1.375	0.422	1.361	0.018	0.014
N/50	0.217	0.720	0.386	1.401	0.048	0.039	N/50	0.377	1.194	0.361	1.182	0.016	0.012

 * Ac in these tables stands for CH₃COO-ion.

DISCUSSION

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table I that hydrated manganese dioxide is negatively charged in contact with dilute solutions of electrolytes containing divalent cations, but the charge is reversed in sign as their concentration is increased. An examination of the data in Table II will also show that although the chloride ions are adsorbed in appreciable quantities, their number is much less than the number of gram ions of the corresponding divalent cation adsorbed. It may be stated in this connection that consistent with the structure of the electrical double layer, consisting of an electrically adsorbed layer and a mobile layer, proposed by Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*) and discussed in a previous paper by Ghosh (*loc. cit.*), two types of adsorption occurring simultaneously of a divalent cation like Ba⁺⁺ should be recognised. In one type a Ba⁺⁺

ion displaces a H^+ ion from its position opposite to a negatively charged point on the surface of MnO_2 and is held bound there. As such a point on the surface is supposed to carry an unit negative charge, the fixation of a Ba^{++} ion opposite to it will necessitate the presence of a chloride ion in its neighbourhood for the maintenance of electrical neutrality in this region. In the other type of adsorption a Ba^{++} ion is supposed to pass from the solution into that part of the double layer which can move when an external electric field is applied. Since in this layer the Ba^{++} ion is free to move, the net effect of its presence therein will be the displacement of two H^+ ions from it, in order that the electrical neutrality of the double layer as a whole is maintained. Thus, the electrical adsorption of a Ba^{++} ion will lead to the liberation of one H^+ ion and the adsorption of one chloride ion, while the adsorption of a Ba^{++} into the mobile part of the double layer will lead to the liberation of two H^+ ions. The adsorption of the cation and the anion and the liberation of acid can therefore be correlated by the following equation,

where M represents the number of a divalent cation A, the number of an univalent anion adsorbed and H, the number of molecules of acid liberated. It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table II that the value of $2M - A$ agrees well with the amount of acid liberated.

Mehrotra and Sen (*loc. cit.*) found that more Cu^{++} ions were adsorbed from a solution of copper sulphate than from a solution of copper chloride of the same concentration by hydrated manganese dioxide. They attributed this phenomenon to the adsorption of anions. It is, however, quite possible that the concentrations of the H^+ ions liberated in such cases may play a more important part than the adsorption of the anion. Thus, H_2SO_4 is known to be a weaker acid than HCl ; and therefore the H^+ ions, which will be displaced by the Cu^{++} ions, will have lower concentration in the $CuSO_4$ than in the $CuCl_2$ solution of the same normality. Therefore, the Cu^{++} ions that are competing with H^+ ions for a place in the mobile sheet of the double layer, or in the electrically adsorbed layer, will have a greater chance of adsorption in presence of $CuSO_4$ solution than in presence of $CuCl_2$ solution, because in the former case the concentration of the free H^+ ions will be less than in the latter case.

The data recorded in Table III fully support this view. It will be noticed that the number of gram cations adsorbed is considerably greater from the solutions of their acetates, than from the solutions of their chlorides under comparable conditions. It will also be noticed that the number of equivalents of acetic acid liberated is considerably greater than the number of gram equivalents of hydrochloric acid liberated, although the adsorption as calculated from equation of the acetate ions is not much different from that of the Cl ions as would account for this marked difference in the adsorption of the cations from their respective solutions. The greater adsorption of the cations from the acetate solution is therefore in our opinion to be attributed mainly to the removal of H^+ ions from the sphere of competition as a result of the formation of undissociated acetic acid molecules.